

EnergyMeasures

Tailored measures supporting energy vulnerable households

D2.4

Periodic update #2 on engagement of energy poor for behaviour change

 <http://www.energymeasures.eu>

 @NRGMeasures

February 2024

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 894759

Document Information

Deliverable ID	2.4		
Deliverable Title	Periodic update #2 on engagement of energy poor for behaviour change		
Lead beneficiary	UCC		
Contributing beneficiaries	DUNE, PON, EIN, KAMPC, SO, PNEC, HABI, ECOE, TIG, OKP.		
Due date Annex I	2024.02.29		
Issue date	2024.02.29		
Dissemination level	Public		
Author(s)	Breffní Lennon		
Document checked	Niall Dunphy	Date:	2024.02.29

Copyright

© 2024 EnergyMeasures Consortium

The EnergyMeasures Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 894759. For more information on the project, its partners, and contributors please see <http://www.energymeasures.eu>.

This report, if not confidential, is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Licence (CC BY 4.0); a copy is available here: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>. You are free to Share – copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format, and Adapt – (remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially. Licence Terms: (i) attribution (you must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the licence, and indicate if changes were made; you may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use); (ii) no additional restrictions (you may not apply legal terms or technological measures that legally restrict others from doing anything the license permits).

Disclaimer

The information contained in this document represents the views of EnergyMeasures consortium as of the date they are published. The EnergyMeasures consortium does not guarantee that any information contained herein is error-free, or up to date, nor makes warranties, express, implied, or statutory, by publishing this document. The information in this document is provided as is and no guarantee or warranty is given that the information is fit for any particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at its sole risk and liability.

The content of this report represents the authors' views only and it is their sole responsibility. It cannot be considered to reflect the views of the European Commission and/or the European Climate Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). The European Commission and the Agency do not accept responsibility for the use that may be made of the information it contains.

EnergyMeasures Consortium

	IE		
	IE		
	NL		
	NL		
	NL		
	BE		
	BE		
	PL		
	MK		
	BG		
	UK		
	AT		

Project Coordinator:

Dr Niall Dunphy, Director, Cleaner Production Promotion Unit, University College Cork, Ireland

T: +353 21 4901969 | e: n.dunphy@ucc.ie | w: www.ucc.ie/cppu

Table of Contents

About EnergyMeasures	5
1 Introduction	7
1.1 Background	7
1.1 Organisation of the report	7
2 Methodology.....	8
3 Country Reports	8
3.1 Belgium	8
3.2 Bulgaria	9
3.3 Ireland.....	10
3.4 Netherlands.....	12
3.5 North Macedonia.....	13
3.6 Poland	14
3.7 United Kingdom.....	15
4 Conclusion.....	16
5 References	17

About EnergyMeasures

EnergyMEASURES is working to address energy poverty in seven European countries, namely: Belgium, Bulgaria, Ireland, Netherlands, North Macedonia, Poland and the United Kingdom. The project comprises two complementary and synergistic strands of work.

The first strand involves working with energy poor households to improve their energy efficiency through a combination of low-cost measures, and changes in energy-related behaviours and practices. Recruited householders will be provided with low-cost energy measures and empowered to change their energy-related behaviours and practices through an approach that takes account of existing housing conditions and is reflective of their lived experience.

The second strand comprises working with municipalities, energy authorities, housing associations and other relevant actors to assess how current multi-level institutional contexts affect efforts to alleviate energy vulnerability in the participating countries. This knowledge will be used to develop and support the implementation of policy and practice measures which will address structural issues that combine to trap households in energy poverty.

Through this work the project contributes to reducing participants' vulnerability to energy poverty, while at the same time cutting household energy consumption and associated GHG emissions.

For more information see <http://www.energymeasures.eu>

Description of the deliverable and its purpose

This deliverable is the final periodic update on the engagement of energy poor for behaviour change for the EnergyMeasures project at month 42 of its work programme (February 2024). The deliverable comprises an overview of the main activities for identification, recruitment, and engagement of energy poor households in each country, a review of the status of engagements, and provides a detailed breakdown of the timeline and updated targets over the 42 months. The task has progressed well in its different engagement activities despite the initial setbacks to household recruitment and engagement associated with the Covid-19. The deliverable outlines progress since the lockdowns and associated restrictions were lifted by each responsible partner.

Glossary

DCENR	Department of the Environment, Climate and Communications
DCC	Dublin City Council
DoA	Description of Action
EA	Energy Action
MABS	Money Advice and Budgeting Service
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
OCMW	The public centre for social welfare in Turnhout
PNEC	Polish Network Energie-Cités
TIG	Tighean Innse Gall
SEAI	Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland
SVdP	Society of St Vincent de Paul
UCC	University College Cork
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

The EnergyMeasures project has worked to implement coordinated household engagement programmes to address the structural issues surrounding energy poverty in seven European countries (Belgium, Bulgaria, Ireland, Netherlands, North Macedonia and the United Kingdom). Consequently, the project has prioritised effort to coordinate with energy poor households to undertake improvements to their energy efficiency through a combination of low-cost measures, and by adjusting their energy-related behaviours and practices.

The work presented in this deliverable has been informed by earlier effort in Task 2.1 where UCC led internal capacity building efforts within the consortium, before undertaking work in Task 2.2 where key indicators characterising those most at-risk of energy poverty were mapped out, and finally Task 2.3 where energy poor and at-risk households were subsequently recruited. A key aim throughout has been to provide householders with low-cost energy measures and to help facilitate their efforts to change their energy-related behaviours and practices that takes into account the nature of the housing units they live in and reflects the lived experiences of those household members.

This document therefore is the culmination of a series of periodic updates on the engagement of energy poor for behaviour change through activities associated with the EnergyMeasures project (see also D2.3 “Periodic update #1 on engagement of energy poor for behaviour change”). Since February 2022, the consortium partners have been able to ramp up their household engagements in the wake of lifting COVID-19 restrictions in the participating countries. This effort was greatly facilitated by the coordinator leading project partners in developing and updating their own individual country engagement plans (see *e.g.*, D7.3 Progress Report: Household engagement plan – Ireland). These country-level engagement plans drew from D1.1 and D1.2, which outline the project’s approach to identifying energy poor households and integrating behaviour change approaches in household engagement respectively.

This deliverable is an update on the reporting set out in D2.3 and provides summary plans of the six focal countries involved in household engagement. These synopses include an overview of the main activities for identification, recruitment, and engagement of energy poor households in each country, a review of the status of engagements, and provides a detailed breakdown of the timeline and updates on the achievement of targets over the intervening period since M18. While the Covid-19 pandemic caused delays with household recruitment and engagement during the first half of the project, this has been largely absent during the intervening months with partners reporting in general quite positively with regards to recruitment and engagement.

1.1 Organisation of the report

This deliverable comprises final reports on the project partners’ efforts towards behaviour change in energy vulnerable households for each of the six participating countries involved in household engagement. While the earlier deliverable (D2.3) provided synopses comprising an overview of the main activities for identification, recruitment, and engagement of energy poor households in each country, Section 3 of this deliverable will provide an update of the status of engagements in each country in addition to an assessment of findings for each focal country.

2 Methodology

The intersecting of a number of key causal factors including low incomes, low levels of residential energy efficiency, and high energy prices are widely accepted as contributing to energy poverty (Boardman 1991). In Deliverable 1.2, Dunphy *et al.* (2020) suggested enhancing this understanding by also focusing on the main structural and contextual conditions that cause energy poverty. As the authors indicate, several interlinking characteristics with energy vulnerable households, or specific life experiences (*e.g.*, sudden ill health) can combine to further worsening their circumstances and undermine the resiliency the householders may have had previously had. Therefore, the importance of empowering householders to effect the change needed to alleviate energy poverty should not be underestimated. Also, current policies, practices, and institutional contexts across multiple decision-making levels all contribute to instances of energy poverty (Bouzarovski *et al.*, 2021). As Velasco-Herrejón *et al.* (2023) suggest, establishing a better understanding of the lived experience of energy poverty is essential in designing any effort to alleviate what is fundamentally a deep-rooted, multi-faceted, and wickedly complex problem. Identifying the most appropriate research methods for discovering a more nuanced understanding of the causal factors is essential. It is against this background, much of the work of EnergyMeasures is informed.

3 Country Reports

3.1 Belgium

In Belgium, more than one household in five is affected by energy poverty. The vast majority of energy-poor households comprise of single people or single-parent families (almost 70%). Single elderly women (+65) and single-parent families headed by a woman are particularly vulnerable. There are also twice as many renters as owners who are affected by energy poverty. The main causes of energy poverty in Belgium are insufficient income, poor housing quality, and rising energy prices. Additional reinforcing factors include a low level of education, a small social network, low technical skills, and a lack of access to the necessary information and services. In recent years, there has been an increase in electricity prices, as well as in the number of instalments plans with energy suppliers and increasingly these instalment plans are not always followed by householders (Koning Boudewijnstichting, 2020).

There are several social housing companies active in Belgium, but the share of social housing is still far too small to cope with the social housing shortage in the country. The waiting time for a social house is four years on average and is still rising. As a result, a large proportion of families with the lowest incomes are forced to rent on the private rental market. Demand far exceeds supply, forcing many poorer tenants to live in substandard housing. The quality of the homes in which the lowest income households live is below average in several respects, these include little or no insulation, more frequent moisture problems (*e.g.*, mould, damp, *etc.*, less space, less comfort, and hardly any renewable energy sources (Heylen & Vanderstraeten, 2019).

SAAMO (previously Samenlevingsopbouw) and Kamp C, worked jointly to implement the EnergyMeasures project in Belgium. Household engagements were originally planned to take place in the city of Turnhout, a medium-sized city in the province of Antwerp, leveraging the support of the city municipality. After a long wait due to COVID-19 related challenges, in December 2021, the organisations signed a contract with the

city/region of Turnhout and the OCMW (the public centre for social welfare in Turnhout) to gain access to the groups targeted for the purpose of the project. However, given the volatility of arising from the COVID-19 pandemic, there is a little uncertainty as regards the level of city municipality activities during the first half of the project. Consequently, an alternate timetable (a Plan B, so to speak) was developed providing for a lower level of activity (see Table 4, p12 of Deliverable 2.3) where it would take a little longer to recruit the country target of 500 households. This plan would require the revision of primary sources of referrals and strategies for increasing recruitment activities on the ground. This strategy is outlined in more detail in D2.3.

However, given the extensive challenges faced by the Belgian cluster during the COVID-19 pandemic and the later failure of repeated actions to produce sufficient referrals (also exasperated by GDPR restrictions) a strategic partnership was established in late 2022 with the Energiesnoeiers (ECs: Energy Cutters) organisation. This collaboration proved very successful on many levels. HERWIN, the ECs' umbrella organisation along with individual ECs, directly engaged with SAAMO & Kamp C to improve their processes, and to professionalise and avail of more small measures through their partnership with the Belgian cluster. Through this collaboration household engagement targets were surpassed. By the end of the project, 598 as opposed to 500 households have been engaged. Most of these household engagements occurred during the collaboration with ECs, with greater outreach was also achieved through targeted referrals via neighbourhood actions organised by SAAMO. In addition, the target area was broadened to include an extra 34 municipalities and enlarging the target area beyond the city and region of Turnhout. These municipalities include: Schilde, Vosselaar, Merksplas, Nijlen (and Kessel), Essen, Kapellen, Beerse, Arendonk, Malle (including Oost-Malle and West-Malle), Retie, Baarle-Hertog, Geel, Mol, Dessel, Herselt, Lille, Westerlo, Kasterlee, Rijkevorsel, Ravels (including Poppel and Weelde), Olen, Hulshout, Herentals, Meerhout, Herenthout, Brasschaat, Wijnegem, Zandhoven, Stabroek, Wilrijk, Tessenderlo, Heist-op-Den-Berg (including Schriek and Booischoot) Wuustwezel (Loenhout) and the city of Lier.

Table 1 Households engagement figures for Belgium up to February 2024

<i>Total of households</i>	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Total
2021			8	4	12
2022	-	-	-	174	174
2023	519	519	598	598	598
2024	598				598
					598

The Home Meter developed by SAAMO was included in the standard ECs' package. In 2022 and 2023 Kamp C and SAAMO were able to provide a larger amount of small measures to the households engaged by the ECs, remedying problems such as the lack of quick access to products due to backlogs at the DSO's end. Extra measures (such as radiator ventilators, blankets, Air Fryers, etc.) were also included with the aim of improving effectiveness with a more enhanced package.

3.2 Bulgaria

Bulgaria has topped the chart on energy poverty for most of the indicators monitored by the EU Energy Poverty Observatory (2020). A large proportion of Bulgarian citizens cannot afford the costs associated with

heating their homes to comfortable temperatures and 33.7% of the population are unable to keep their homes sufficiently warm (with all the adverse health effects this causes) – the highest rate in the EU. The same applies to the share of households that cannot afford cooling during the summer – some 49.5% of the population. While Greece has the highest share of the population with overdue energy bills, Bulgaria is a close second at 31.7%. All factors that determine the level of energy poverty including low incomes, high energy prices (compared to the purchasing power of the population), and poor energy performance of buildings (over 90% being in energy classes D, E, F and lower) come into play in relation to Bulgaria. Although progress has been made in recent years, especially through the National Program for Energy Efficiency in Multifamily Residential Buildings, energy poverty in Bulgaria remains the most severe. Bulgarian residential buildings are some of the most energy inefficient in Europe. Recent analyses undertaken by the local NGO, EnEffect, and based official data by the National Statistical Institute on the population’s income and consumption figures for 2018, shows that more than 50% of the Bulgarian population are at risk of energy poverty.

The Municipal Energy Efficiency Network, EcoEnergy, is a non-profit association of Bulgarian municipalities, providing technical support and assistance for the successful design and implementation of local energy and climate policies, to increase energy security and promote sustainable development at a local and regional level. EcoEnergy focuses on lower-income householders in multi-family apartment buildings in Gabrovo and Burgas (c. 28.5k and 119k households respectively). Working through its energy projects and with linked third parties it has been able to identify and recruit energy poor households above the original target of 600 households to 723 households.

EcoEnergy, Burgas and Gabrovo municipalities were able to leverage their existing networks to engage with householders in multifamily apartment buildings in the two cities. The EnergyMeasures project was promoted to the target groups by liaising with local authorities and homeowner’s organisations through emails, phone calls and meetings. Municipal communications offices were also contacted to publicise the project on local radio and newspapers, using its substantial internet and social media presence, along with NGOs and civil society groups that were attracted to publicise and otherwise support the project.

Table 2 Households engagement figures for Bulgaria up to February 2024

<i>Total of households</i>	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Total
2021			145	189	334
2022	723	723	723	723	723
2023	723	723	723	723	723
2024	723				723
					723

3.3 Ireland

Depending on the metric used, the Irish government’s Energy Poverty Strategy suggests that the rate of households experiencing energy poverty in Ireland is between 8.8% based on self-reported inability to heat, and 28% derived from modelled expenditure and building energy rating data (DCENR, 2016). One of the two leading Irish partners during the first half of the project, Energy Action CLG (EA) was founded in 1988 with

the main aim of helping alleviate fuel poverty in Ireland by addressing the thermal needs of disadvantaged householders. Energy Action's primary target group for EnergyMeasures was elderly people living in single-family, owner-occupied houses in a large urban area, namely Dublin City and its environs. The organisation was tasked with recruiting 500 households by tapping into their existing networks including SEAI, DCC, Housing Associations and NGOs including MABS, SVdP to engage with target householders. As a result, household recruiting activities have included the distribution of 10,000 leaflets with information about the project and energy advice at key locations such as Senior Citizen Complexes, MABS, SVdP, Senior Citizen Groups, Friends of the Elderly, Age Action, Third Age Ireland, ALONE, Irish Environmental Network, Environmental Protection Agency.

Earlier plans included the involvement of two Local Authorities to access the relevant target groups. However, the COVID-19 pandemic had a serious impact on gaining access to households due to the stop of in-person municipal services. Additionally, the scheme of the Pandemic Unemployment Payments limited Energy Actions ability to recruit staff members that will work as energy advisors. EA had planned to broaden recruitment activities over the second half of the project to include training city wardens and caretakers on the importance of energy efficiency measures to empower them to identify and encourage energy-saving practices in their complexes. Also, organising an energy efficiency competition between EnergyMeasures and participating senior citizen complexes in addition to national energy suppliers have been contacted to support the EnergyMeasures project recruitment efforts. However, these plans had to be radically curtailed or reenvisioned due to EA's voluntary liquidation in November 2022, through after careful planning and coordination between the remaining partners, notably UCC and PNEC, the staff member from EA leading the engagements in Dublin joined PNEC after it took over the coordination responsibilities for Dublin activities. The former EA staff member was then able to adjust his efforts to recruitment and engagements in accordance with the new scenario.

In Cork, the UCC target group comprised disadvantaged communities in Cork City (c. 70k households), which University College Cork have traditionally engaged in educational and social outreach programmes. The unit had planned to build on these existing contacts to implement an outreach programme involving university staff (*e.g.*, maintenance and technical personnel) volunteering to undertake low-cost measures for energy poor households in Cork City. However, the legacy of the COVID-19 pandemic meant UCC had to pivot away from this plan and instead worked with the new PNEC staff member to develop a new strategy leveraging relationships already established with national energy suppliers on an alternative plan (from more information, see D3.4)

UCC's household recruiting activities included liaising with local organisations including, Carbery Housing Association and NCE Energy Hub, to engage them as gatekeepers for the project in their localities. This also involved distributing leaflets in target areas, and contacting University student societies and the UCC Media and Communications Office to publicise the initiative on local radio and newspapers, through its substantial web and social media presence. Gatekeeper organisations were also able to publicise the project and refer energy households to the project team.

Given the extensive 'lock-downs' and social restrictions imposed in Ireland to mitigate the impacts of COVID-19, the engagement in Ireland had to be rescheduled to fit in with the planned 'reopening' of society as the

vaccination programme progressed and the pandemic threat lessened. Accordingly, the post-lockdown period saw significant ramping up of Cork figures due to the extra resources UCC applied to this effort.

Table 3 Households engagement figures for Dublin up to February 2024

Total of households	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Total
2021			-	7	7
2022	16	-	150	184	184
2023	207	263	286	364	364
2024	364				364
					364

Table 4 Households engagement figures for Cork up to February 2024

Total of households	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Total
2021			-	9	9
2022	22	-	115	197	197
2023	197	197	220	239	239
2024	239				239
					239

3.4 Netherlands

Energy poverty is a relatively new term used in policy circles in the Netherlands even though it has been demonstrated that energy poverty occurs in the country (Breukers *et al.*, 2021; Straver *et al.*, 2017). Policy initiatives have begun to emerge in various parts of the country, often initiated by local municipalities. Housing corporations, energy cooperatives, and other social organisations are also increasingly tackling energy poverty issues. However, there are still no national programs or strategies aimed at reducing energy poverty in the Netherlands, although the pressure to do so has been increasing (Straver *et al.*, 2021). Within Eindhoven, Energiebox is one initiative that has had a long trajectory providing households with energy-saving advice and supports.

The municipality of Eindhoven (Gemeente Eindhoven), PON & Telos and DuneWorks worked in the city of Eindhoven targeting households that are energy and income poor. The three organisations initial aim was to recruit 400 households using conventional media, social media, and direct personal contact with households and local communities. Conventional media included press releases, local newspapers (Eindhoven's Dagblad or neighbourhood newspaper), and newsletters from supporting (neighbourhood) partners. Social media comprised information in a Facebook Group and applicable WhatsApp group and direct contact with households was planned through targeted door-to-door contact and meetings. The municipality of Eindhoven also leveraged their existing initiatives, networks, NGOs, and other partners such as Foodbanks, church organisations, and initiatives providing social benefits and financial arrangements for the disadvantaged to identify and refer households to the project.

Household engagement only really took off when an energy crisis broke out in the autumn of 2022, and everyone was confronted with significant price increases. In January 2023 we reached our final goal of 400

participating households. Table 5 lists the three organisation's efforts to recruit households up to February 2024.

Table 5 Households engagement figures for the Netherlands up to February 2024

<i>Total of households</i>	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Total
2021				19	19
2022	-	-	267	326	326
2023	372	392	403	403	403
2024	403				403
					403

3.5 North Macedonia

Energy is used inefficiently in North Macedonia, with energy intensity significantly above the European average. The high energy intensity is a result of aged and often obsolete energy infrastructure and poorly maintained and/or outdated energy-using capital stock – especially in buildings. Residential multi-apartment buildings, estimated at 11,500 in North Macedonia, account for a significant share of the total energy consumption in buildings and are at the same time highly energy inefficient. According to recent findings of the Western Balkans Residential Energy Efficiency Market Assessment, the penetration rates of energy-efficient materials, appliances and equipment is very low in North Macedonia (on average not exceeding 10%), especially in households with lower incomes. Most of the buildings in North Macedonia are between 30 to 50 years old, lack thermal insulation, and have poor energy performance. About 6% of all residential building stock in North Macedonia is estimated to meet the national energy performance requirements and belong to energy class C or D. All other residential buildings can be classified in lower energy classes thus emphasising the need for substantial cross-sectoral energy efficiency retrofitting. Technical opportunities for improving energy efficiency in existing buildings are significant with potential energy savings estimated at between 30-70%. Furthermore, experience indicates there is low awareness of and knowledge of energy efficiency measures and the available financing supports available among households.

Habidom is a residential building management company that aims to improve the living conditions in collective residential buildings. The organisation has particularly targeted two vulnerable groups: female-headed and elderly couples households living in multi-family apartment buildings and living on low incomes. Households have been recruited through the distributing of leaflets in residential buildings already managed by Habidom (146 residential apartment buildings which have a total of 3,602 households).

Table 6 Households engagement figures for North Macedonia up to February 2024

<i>Total of households</i>	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Total
2021			-	30	30
2022	-	-	175	358	358
2023	424	510	540	620	620
2024	620				620
					620

3.6 Poland

At present, some 4.6 million people in Poland live in energy poverty, accounting for 12% of the population. Particularly vulnerable groups include: (1) people living in the countryside, (2) young families on their first job (or seeking work), (3) residents of disadvantaged urban areas, and (4) elderly and disabled people. The first group represents two thirds of all energy poor, while the last group accounts for a quarter of the total. Also, the associated risk of falling into energy poverty is considerably higher for households living on social benefits than for other socio-economic groups.

The Association of Municipalities Polish Network “Energie Cités” (PNEC) is a non-governmental organisation which has, since 1994, supported sustainable energy planning and local development at the local level across Poland. PNEC implemented the EnergyMeasures project in the city of Bielsko-Biała, in cooperation with city authorities. PNEC also targeted two main groups there, comprising private owners occupying single-family buildings and private owners of flats in multi-family buildings (both with the focus on the elderly and families living on social benefits). Due to the lack of data to assist in identifying energy poor households, the selection/recruitment of households was decided according to two criteria: (1) the net income per person, and (2) the technical condition of the building.

PNEC’s household recruiting activities included a multi-channel campaign to inform the general public about the project using traditional and social media, and a strategy for involving stakeholders. Traditional media comprised of project information hosted on the city website, the city newsletter, local free bulletins, housing association bulletins, and community housing association and church notice boards. Also, PNEC contacted local independent media (like “Kronika Beskidzka”, “Dziennik Zachodni”, Radio Bielsko) and established clear channels for promoting the project with local residents. The text and the graphics of the advertisement was co-designed jointly between PNEC and the city of Bielsko-Biała. The social media campaign complemented traditional media by reaching young people through Facebook pages, posts and on local groups. The aim of the stakeholder involvement strategy was to reach households through institutions such as the Municipal Social Services Office, local schools, housing associations, churches, seniors clubs, relevant NGOs (*e.g.*, focusing on social issues and in particular energy-related topics). Most of the households registered for the project were recruited through municipal channels by filling an application form offline, which was then relayed back to PNEC.

Table 7 Households engagement figures for Poland up to February 2024

<i>Total of households</i>	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Total
2021			-	-	-
2022	18	-	-	450	450
2023	450	450	450	450	450
2024	450				450
					450

3.7 United Kingdom

In 2019 an estimated 24.6% (around 613,000 households) of all households in Scotland were in fuel poverty. Between 2018 and 2019, rates of fuel poverty increased in remote rural areas (from 33% to 43%), widening the gap between urban (24%) and rural deprivation (29%). Similarly, levels of extreme fuel poverty increased in remote rural areas from 23% to 33%, pushing the extreme fuel poverty rates in rural areas (at 19%) to far higher rates than in urban areas (11%). Overall rates of fuel poverty differed between the social (37%) and private sector (20%) although rates of extreme fuel poverty were similar (14% and 12%, respectively) in 2019. Levels of fuel poverty among households using electricity as their primary heating source have remained the highest, at 43%, compared to households using gas (22%), oil (28%) and other fuel types (31%) as their primary heating fuel in 2019.

Tighean Innse Gall (TIG) was founded in 1991 to help make homes affordably warm, safe to live in and adapted for those with disabilities or who are frail. The primary focus of TIG engagements has been the Outer Hebrides of Scotland, targeting mainly private owner-occupiers suffering from energy poverty and living in remote communities on the islands. Additionally, there has been particular focus on the elderly (65+).

TIG's household recruitment strategy focused on creating public awareness and involving service agencies. Raising public awareness about the project has been done through placing adverts in local newspapers, social media, local radio stations (one in Gaelic) and word of mouth. TIG also involved agencies that provide services for people throughout the islands so that they could promote EnergyMEASURES and refer households to the project. These agencies include the Western Isles National Health Service (WINHS), Western Isles Association for Mental Health (WIAMH), Western Isles Citizens Advice Service (WICAS), The Shed (works with people with drug and alcohol addiction issues), and The Foyer which works with vulnerable young people. In addition to these, the Financial Inclusion Team of Comhairle nan Eilean Siar and other local community-based organisations were also engaged to reach the target households.

These various outreach activities have resulted in successful recruitment of households in excess of the original target figure. However, it should be noted those reached was far beyond those captured in Table 8 below as some households recruited were deemed not eligible for support using the criteria set down by the project. Nonetheless those not eligible were given advice and signposted to other agencies such as Home Energy Scotland who deliver interest free loans for larger home energy efficiency measures and upgrades.

Table 8 Households engagement figures for the United Kingdom (Scotland) up to February 2024

Total of households	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Total
2021	148	49	64	120	383
2022	45	-	180	234	234
2023	290	297	435	511	511
2024	511				511
					511

4 Conclusion

Based on the knowledge developed in T2.2, the household engagement process of T2.3 involved project staff and volunteers working with householders to get an overall assessment of their dwelling, ascertain their energy consumption, and understand their energy-related practices and behaviours. As part of this process, householders engaged with consortium partners, agreeing on a tailored range of low-cost energy measures and behaviour changes. These were selected from a portfolio of possible measures, which included a range of energy efficient devices including LED lighting, water saving faucets, shower timers, meters; energy conservation measures including draught proofing, hot water lagging, radiator foil, device standby killers; and energy services including the servicing of heating systems, where applicable.

Based on this assessment, and with the support of a behaviour change plan checklist, the energy advisors and householders were then able to co-design a bespoke energy behaviour change plan and a package of low-cost energy measures that matched their lived experiences around energy. To do this we applied lessons and information gathered in T2.2 to deconstruct habitual patterns of energy use to help households become conscious of the factors that underpin their choices and in turn help them to adopt new patterns of energy use. In the case of multi-family dwellings, some of this work was routed through homeowner associations, which provided an additional collective dimension to the project with individual behaviour change supported and reinforced by the actions of peers *etc.*

To support these household engagement activities, the partners developed country-specific implementation plans which detailed (i) how energy poor householders will be identified and recruited, and (ii) the step-by-step approach to be taken when engaging householders. The COVID-19 pandemic did have a significant impact on the partners' ability to recruit and engage householders, especially during the first half of the project. However, once pandemic-related restrictions were lifted, project partners were able to meet their engagement targets. In this context, the project did undergo significant rescheduling of tasks, modification of recruitment strategies, and where applicable modification of associated deadlines. This enabled the project partners to make up for the recruitment and engagement delays early on in the project. Indeed, these remedial measures enabled most partners to ultimately exceed their original targets.

5 References

- Bouzarovski, S. *et al.* (2020) *Towards an inclusive energy transition in the European Union : Confronting energy poverty amidst a global crisis*. Third pan-EU energy poverty report of the EU Energy Poverty Observatory. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2833/103649>.
- Bouzarovski, S., Thomson, H., & Cornelis, M. (2021). Confronting Energy Poverty in Europe: A Research and Policy Agenda. *Energies*, 14(4), 858. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14040858>
- Breukers, S., Crosbie, T., & Summeren, L. van. (2020). Mind the gap when implementing technologies intended to reduce or shift energy consumption in blocks-of-buildings. *Energy & Environment*, 31(4), 613–633. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0958305X19881361>
- DCENR. (2016). *Energy Poverty Strategy*. Dublin: Department of Communications, Energy & Natural Resources.
- Dünnhoff, E., Eisenmann, L. and Schäferbarthold, U. (2010) Guidelines: Introducing Advisory Services on how to Save Energy for Low-income Households (translated for ACHIEVE). Heidelberg /Frankfurt am Main: Institut für Energie- und Umweltforschung Heidelberg GmbH and Caritasverband Frankfurt e.V.
- EPOV. (2020). *Indicator / EU Energy Poverty Observatory*. <https://www.energypoverty.eu/observatory-documents/ireland>
- Kerr, N., Gillard, R. and Middlemiss, L. (2019) ‘Politics, problematisation, and policy: A comparative analysis of energy poverty in England, Ireland and France’, *Energy and Buildings*. Elsevier B.V., 194, pp. 191– 200. doi: 10.1016/j.enbuild.2019.04.002.
- Soaita, A. M. and McKee, K. (2020) ‘Researching Home’s Tangible and Intangible Materialities by Photo- Elicitation’, *Housing, Theory and Society*. Routledge, 00(00), pp. 1–21. doi: 10.1080/14036096.2020.1738543.
- Storm-Mathisen, A. (2018) ‘Visual Methods in Ethnographic Fieldwork–On Learning from Participants Through their Video-accounts’, *Forum for Development Studies*. Taylor & Francis, 45(2), pp. 261–286. doi: 10.1080/08039410.2018.1450287.
- Straver, K., Siebinga, A., Mastop, J., De Lidth, M., Vethman, P., & Uyterlinde M. (2017). Rapportage Energiearmoede. Effectieve interventies om energie efficiëntie te vergroten en energiearmoede te verlagen. ECN Reports
- Thomson, H., Snell, C. and Bouzarovski, S. (2017) ‘Health, Well-Being and Energy Poverty in Europe: A Comparative Study of 32 European Countries’, *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute, 14(6), p. 584.

Vanderstraeten, L. & Heylen, K. (2019), 'De woonsituatie in Vlaanderen. Gaan we erop vooruit?',
De Gids op Maatschappelijk Gebied, vol. 110, no. 5, pp. 22-31.

Velasco-Herrejón, P., Lennon, B., & Dunphy, N. P. (Eds.) (2023). *Living with Energy Poverty*.
Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003408536>